

Acknowledgement

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Chemical Investigation of *Ougeinia dalbergioides*

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REINVESTIGATION of the heartwood of *Ougeinia dalbergioides* has yielded genistein, ferreirin, neophellamuretin, orobol and wedelolactone in addition to compounds already reported¹⁻³. This is the first report of the natural occurrence of neophellamuretin in free state and wedelolactone is a rare metabolite. The findings are placed below in Table 1.

TABLE 1—IDENTIFICATION OF COMPOUNDS IN *O. dalbergioides*

Compound isolated	m.p. °C (Solvent of crystallisation)	Literature reference
Homoferreirin	166-67 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	1
Genistein	300 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	5
Ougenin	239-41 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	1
Ferreirin	210-11 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	5
Neophellamuretin	189-91 (EtOAc/petroleum ether)	3
Dalbergiodin	230-32 (EtOAc/C ₆ H ₆)	1
Orobol	270-72 (EtOAc)	5
Kaempferol	275-77 (MeOH/CHCl ₃)	2
Wedelolactone	327-30 (MeOH)	4

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The ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) of neophellamuretin acetate (Ac₂O/Py) displayed the following peaks (δ): 7.50 (d, 2H, J=8.5Hz, H-2', H-6'), 7.18 (d, 2H, J=8.5Hz, H-3', H-5'), 6.62 (s, 1H, H-6), 5.45, 5.75 (2d, 1H each, J=12.5Hz, H-2, H-3), 5.10 (br, 1H, CH of prenyl), 3.25 (d, 2H, J=7.5Hz, CH₂ of prenyl), 2.38 (s, 3H, phenolic acetoxy), 2.32 (s, 6H, two phenolic acetoxy), 2.02 (s, 3H, aliphatic acetoxy), 1.55, 1.68 (2s, 6H, gem methyls). The identity as neophellamuretin was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample of neophellamuretin kindly gifted by Prof. M. Hasegawa who had isolated³ phellamurin (neophellamuretin glycoside) from *Phelladendron amurense* (Rutaceae).

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Solvent Extraction of Uranium(VI) with Versatic 911

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CONSIDERABLE interest has developed in recent years on the extraction of metals with high molecular weight carboxylic acids¹. In this communication, a rapid and selective method for the extraction of uranium(VI) with liquid cation exchanger, Versatic 911, in benzene is reported. Uranium(VI) has been quantitatively extracted at pH 5.5-6.0 from 0.1 M acetate solution with 1.81 M Versatic 911. The effect of variables such as pH, diluent, contact time, extractant concentration and acetate ion concentration has been investigated. The organic phase has been stripped with 2 M nitric acid. A probable composition of the extracted species, UO₂R₂.2RH (RH = Versatic 911), has been proposed. The presence of manganese(II), iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), zinc(II), cadmium(II), silver(I),